

USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN HISTORY TEACHING METHODOLOGY

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Abstract. *This article analyzes the methods of using innovative technologies in history and their impact on the educational process. Ways to enliven and engage students in history lessons will be explored through digital resources and multimedia tools, educational platforms and online resources, gamification elements, and technologies such as artificial intelligence and adaptive learning systems. The article sheds light on the ways in which the study of history can be made interesting and effective with the help of innovative technologies.*

Keywords: *innovative technologies, history teaching methodology, digital resources, multimedia tools, online educational platforms, gaming (Gamification), artificial intelligence, adaptive educational systems.*

The science of history helps us understand the present through the study of past events, processes, and individuals. However, traditional history teaching methods often do not arouse students' interest and prevent them from gaining deep knowledge. Therefore, the use of innovative technologies is gaining importance in the history teaching methodology. This article analyzes the methods of using innovative technologies in history education and their impact on the educational process.

Innovative technologies and their role in teaching history

Digital resources and multimedia tools

Digital resources and multimedia tools play an important role in enlivening history lessons and engaging students. Such tools include:

Interactive Maps: Using interactive maps to show past territorial changes and geographic events. This allows students to visualize the information and retain it in their memory for a long time. For example, Google Earth and other digital mapping programs allow students to virtually explore historic areas. **Videos and documentaries:** Films depicting historical events can give students a more complete picture of a particular period or person. This method engages students in the learning process and makes history come alive for them. For example, documentaries made by the BBC and National Geographic explain historical subjects in a clear and interesting way. **Virtual Reality (VR) and Augmented Reality (AR):** With the help of VR and AR technologies, students can virtually visit historical sites and experience the events of that era. These technologies help to visualize historical events and places more accurately. For example, through apps like Google Expeditions, students can virtually tour historical sites using VR goggles.

Educational platforms and online resources

Online learning platforms and resources create endless opportunities for students. These technologies include: **MOOC (Massive Open Online Courses):** Through online courses, students can gain in-depth knowledge of history according to their interests. Platforms like Coursera, edX, and Udacity offer history courses offered by various universities. **E-Books and Articles:** Through e-libraries, students have easy access to historical sources and scholarly articles. Platforms such

as Google Books, JSTOR, and Project Gutenberg provide comprehensive historical materials for students. Forums and Discussion Groups: Online forums and discussion groups on social media encourage knowledge sharing and exchange of views on historical issues among students. Through Reddit, Quora, and other platforms, students can hold discussions on historical topics.

3. Gamification

Adding game elements to the educational process helps to increase the interest of students and make their learning more effective. Game elements include: Historical strategic games: Studying historical events and processes through strategic games becomes more interesting for students. For example, games like Civilization and Age of Empires allow students to try historical strategies. Quizzes and Tests: Through online quizzes and tests, students can test their knowledge and assess themselves. Platforms like Quizlet and Kahoot allow teachers to create and administer interactive tests. Project-Based Learning: Students explore historical topics in depth and develop presentation skills through projects and research. This method develops their research skills and encourages independent learning. Artificial intelligence and adaptive learning systems. Artificial intelligence and adaptive learning systems provide the opportunity to provide education according to the individual needs of students:

Artificial Intelligence (AI): AI systems can create personalized learning programs for students, help them and identify their weaknesses. For example, platforms like Knewton and Smart Sparrow create individual learning paths for students.

Adaptive learning systems: These systems evaluate the knowledge acquired by the students and adjust the teaching strategies according to their needs. This helps students get the learning material at the right level for them and increases their success.

Conclusion: The use of innovative technologies in the methodology of teaching history is important for increasing the interest of students and making their learning more effective. Digital resources, online learning platforms, gamification elements, and artificial intelligence can make history lessons more alive and interesting. These methods make the teaching process easier and more effective not only for students, but also for teachers. Through the use of innovative technologies, we can create opportunities for future generations to study history in a deeper and more interesting way.

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